

Agroecological Solutions for
Resilient Farming in West Africa

Baseline Survey (WP2)

FGDs and KIIs Guide – Final Version

(Appendix G of CIRAWA_D2.2_Socio-Econ. and Env. Analysis_V.6.0_2024_06_29)

CIRAWA Project Information Leaflet

1. The Project is “CIRAWA – Agroecological Solutions for Resilient Farming in West Africa”. It is an European Commission Horizon 2020 funded research project with a main aim of unlocking the potential of agroecology practices in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices.
2. The research is being undertaken in four West African countries - Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal and The Gambia - by 14 Partners from West Africa and Europe, with Fundacion CARTIF of Spain as Coordinator.
3. The research is strictly for development and academic purposes and will have no negative consequences on any person or group of persons. Part or all of the information given might be published in books, journals or other suitable academic outlets but will not be traced to anybody providing information.
4. Participation in the research is completely voluntary, and no negative consequences will arise from refusal to participate, or from withdrawing from participation if the need arises at any time during Project implementation.
5. Every person is advised to fully consider, with others if necessary, and prior to participation, any disadvantages, side effects, risks and/or discomforts that may arise from participation in the research before consenting to take part.
6. Unless specifically agreed otherwise, all information disclosed will be carefully made anonymous.
7. All information or data obtained will be held as confidential and will not be distributed to third parties other than through the normal process of information dissemination.
8. The Project has an internationally recognized professional as the Ethics Advisor, who is entirely independent of the research, and any dissatisfaction with any aspect of the conduct of the research may be referred to him/her.
9. **You are being asked to participate in the baseline survey of the Project.**

Do you consent to participate 1) Yes 2) No

Thank you!

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) Guides
(Final)

Main Topics for Discussions

1. Farming activities (types of crops, livestock, aquaculture, cultivation practices etc) and other livelihood activities of community members
2. Agricultural production constraints (crops and livestock): Soils, Water, Inputs, Marketing etc.
3. Irrigation – Types and extent
4. Access of women and youth to production resources
5. Wealth and poverty of communities and members
6. Awareness and perception of changes in local climatic conditions
7. Farmers’ perception of changes of natural environment over time
8. Agroecological, climate smart (CS) and Sustainable Land Management (SLM) practices
9. Agro-waste valorisation
10. Anti-environment practices
11. Natural resource conflicts
12. Use of digital tools

1. Farming activities (types of crops, livestock, aquaculture and cultivation practices etc) and other livelihood activities of community members

- a) Please explain to us the farming and other activities (by men, women and youth) in this area (community).
- b) Are you satisfied with your farming activities ? Why or why not?
- c) Are you satisfied with other livelihood activities ? Why or why not?

d) Main crops cultivated and estimated yields:

Main crops	Cultivation practices (land preparation planting, weed control, etc. methods)	Estimated yields (per acre)	How satisfied with yields? 1) Very satisfied 2) Satisfied 3)	If dissatisfied what should be done?

			Somehow satisfied 4) Dissatisfied	

e) Main livestock raised (Any aquaculture?)

Main livestock raised/ fishes produced	Indicate the products produced	How satisfied are you with production? 1) Very satisfied 2) Satisfied 3) Somehow satisfied 4) Dissatisfied	If dissatisfied what should be done?

2. Agricultural production constraints (crops and livestock): Soils, Water, Inputs, Marketing etc.

a) Rank the main agricultural production constraints faced in the area (from most severe to least)?

Production constraint	Rank	What can be done and by who to reduce or remove constraint?
	1	
	2	
	3	
	4	
	5	
	6	

	7	
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- b) How will you describe the soils in the community?
 - 1) Very good (fertile) 2) Fertile 3) Somehow fertile 4) Poor 5) Very poor
- c) What has caused the soils to be what they are?
- d) What can you or anybody do about the present state of the soil?

YOU MAY ASK SIMILAR QUESTIONS WITH RESPECT TO OTHER CONSTRAINTS!

3. Irrigation – Types and extent

- a) Do people in the community undertake irrigated agriculture?
- b) If yes, explain the types and extent (area, yields etc), who are involved (Government, NGOs, pprivate sector etc), and any difficulties faced.
- c) What can be done to improve irrigated agriculture in the area?

4. Access of women and youth to production resources

- a) What special or specific constraints do **women** face with respect to agricultural production/marketing etc. activities in the area?
- b) What special or specific constraints do **youth** face with respect to agricultural production/marketing etc. activities?
- c) What should be done to improve access of women and youth to production resources and to remove or reduce the constraints they face?

5. Wealth and poverty of communities and members

- a) About what percentage (proportion) of the people in this community will you consider as:
 - (1) Very rich%
 - (2) Rich%
 - (3) Average %
 - (4) Poor %
 - (5) Very poor %
- b) Which category of persons are considered rich or wealthy in the community?
- c) What can be done by you and/or any other person or persons to reduce the poverty of the members of the community?

6. Awareness and perception of changes in local climatic conditions

- a) Explain (or discuss) the local climatic changes over time in this locality.
- b) What do you think is responsible for the situation?
- c) What do you think can be done to improve/better the existing climatic situation?

7. Farmers' perception of changes of natural environment over time

a) Which of these items were known, produced, used and/or available in the area 10, 30 and 50 years ago but are no longer seen.

1.0 Item	1.1 About 10 years ago	1.2 About 30 years ago	1.3 About 50+ years ago	1.4 What are the reasons for their disappearance?	What is the situation now? 1. Better (improving) 2) Same 3) Getting worse (deteriorating)
1. Crops (consider varieties)					
2. Trees					
4. Shrubs					
5. Livestock (consider breeds)					
6. Wildlife					
7. Water bodies/wetlands					
8. Farming systems (production practices)					

b) Which of these items are now available but were not known in the area in the past 10, 30 and 50 years ago?

1.0 Item	1.1 Now available but not known in the past (i.e introduced crops, trees etc.)	1.2 What are the reasons for the appearance of these crops/trees/shrubs/livestock/wildlife?
1. Crops (consider varieties)		
2. Trees		
4. Shrubs		

5. Livestock (consider breeds)		
6. Wildlife		
7. Water bodies/wetlands		
8. Farming systems (production practices)		

8. Agroecological, climate smart (CS) and sustainable land management (SLM) practices

a) Please provide the following information with respect to agroecological, CS and SLM Practices in this area

	Types (which crops and/or livestock)	In a ranking of 1 to 5 (1 is best), indicate the usefulness of these practices.	What do you consider to be the most important benefit of the	Any trainings in the practices? What types of trainings?	Did women participate in the trainings? How many or what proportion of	What proportion of farmers practice the method in the community/district?		Explain the advantages and disadvantages of the practices
						Women farmers	Men farmers	

		Give reasons for the ranking.	practice? (see codes below)	When? By who?	trainees were women?			
Intercropping (mixed cropping)								
Crop rotation								
Mulching								
Manure application								
Mixed farming								
Contour farming								
Agroforestry								
Minimum/No tillage								
Cover cropping (e.g. use of mucuna, canavalia etc)								
Crop-livestock integration (improved mixed farming)								
Integrated pest management								
Other (Specify)								
Other (specify)								

Codes: 1) Soil fertility improvement 2) Soil water retention 3) Erosion control 4) Other (specify)

b) Please identify persons, groups, organizations etc. that may be described as **“agroecology champions”** (good practitioners of agroecology, climate smart and sustainable land maangement).

9. Agro-waste valorisation

a) What use is made of the following agro-wastes?

Agro-wastes	What use is made of waste? Or What is the waste used for?
Cereals (stovers- husks, stalks, cobs etc.)	
Legumes (stovers)	
Grasses	
Trees (forest) waste (e.g. leaves etc)	
Animal manure (cow dung, chicken manure etc)	
Wastes from abattoirs	
Kitchen wastes	
Other wastes (specify)	

b) What quantities are generated per acre, period available, and what processing carried out?

Agro-wastes	Quantity generated per acre (% of harvest gathered as waste)	Period available (months of the year)	What processing carried out?	Challenges faced

Cereals ((stovers- husks, stalks, cobs etc.)				
Legumes (stovers)				
Grasses				
Tree/Forest waste				
Animal manure (cow dung, chicken manure etc)				
Wastes from abattoirs				
Kitchen wastes				
Other wastes (specify)				

10. Anti-environment practices – Reasons and what should be done to reduce prevalence

Practice	Reasons for the practices	What should be done and by who to reduce practices
Deforestation (Illegal logging/charcoal production)		

and firewood cutting)		
Bush burning (fires)		
Burning of farm residues		
Use of agrochemical in farms (especially weedicides)		
Use of agrochemical in water bodies		
Illegal/small scale mining		
Sand winning/stone quarrying		
Others (Specify)		
Other (specify)		

11. Natural resources use conflicts

Discuss conflicts over use of common resources (farmland, water, grassland, economic trees etc.) in the district/community (especially conflicts between farmers and pastoralists):

- i) What natural resource conflicts have occurred in this district/community? (e.g. water sources in the district/community, farming/grazing land in the district/community etc)
- ii) How many times per year on average?
- iii) Explain the circumstances (causes, degree etc.) and the consequences.
- iv) How have such conflicts been resolved?

12. Use of digital tools

a) Which of these digital tools are used by men, women and the youth in the households?

Tool	Men – 1) Yes 2) No	Women 1) Yes 2) No	Youth 1) Yes 2) No
Non-smart phones			

Radio (access to radio e.g. phones)			
Television (TV)			
Smart phone (Voice)			
Smart phone (Voice and SMS)			
Smart phone (Voice, SMS and WhatsApp)			
Smart phone (Voice, SMS, WhatsApp +)			
Computer (No email)			
Computer (email)			
Other (specify)			

b) Explain how you (farmers) use these digital tools to support your (their) agricultural production, marketing etc.